

REALISM AND THE GREAT LAKES REGION OF AFRICA'S UNSTABLE SECURITY: AN ANALYSIS AT THREE LEVELS

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RESEARCH ARTICLE

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Abstract

This paper examines the enduring security challenges in the Great Lakes Region of Africa through the lens of realist theory. By analyzing the interplay of power, interests, and state behaviour at the individual, national, and international levels, the study sheds light on the factors contributing to the region's persistent instability. The paper argues that the pursuit of self-interest by leaders, the competition among states, and the influence of external powers have exacerbated tensions and fueled conflict. Despite various peace initiatives and international interventions, the region remains vulnerable to renewed cycles of violence. A more comprehensive understanding of the region's security dynamics requires a nuanced analysis incorporating realist and non-realist perspectives.

Keywords: Realism, Great Lakes Region, Security dilemma, Power maximization, Rivalry cooperation, Natural resources

1. Introduction

The Great Lakes region in Africa, encompassing countries such as the Democratic Republic of Congo, Rwanda, Burundi and Uganda, has been the theatre of persistent conflicts, political instability and humanitarian crises for decades. This complex situation has repercussions not only for the nations concerned but also for the stability of the African continent as a whole. Understanding the security dynamics of this region is, therefore, essential to developing effective strategies aimed at establishing lasting peace.

This study is part of previous research on security in the Great Lakes region, which adopted a realistic perspective to analyze the instability factors. Previous work has highlighted the deep causes of conflicts, such as ethnic rivalries, competition for natural resources and foreign interference. For example, a Center for Conflict Resolution publication highlights the importance of governance and security in this region (Levine & Nagar, 2015). Our analysis is distinguished by offering a three-level approach: local, state, and international. This approach provides a more nuanced understanding of complex interactions that feed insecurity.

The main hypotheses of this study are based on the idea that the dynamics of power within states, interstate relationships, and the influences of international actors contribute significantly to regional instability. Secondly, we apply the idea that peace initiatives must be adapted to each of these levels to be effective. These hypotheses are anchored in the realistic theory of international relations, which emphasizes the pursuit of national interest and the centrality of power in interactions between actors.

The research design is structured to systematically examine these three levels of analysis. At the local level, we studied community dynamics and internal conflicts. At the state level, we analyzed government policies and bilateral relations between the region's states. Finally, at the international level, we assessed the impact of interventions by international organizations and foreign powers. This holistic approach links hypotheses to empirical realities observed at each level.

The theoretical implications of this study reside in the enrichment of the literature on realism in international relations, which demonstrates how this theory can be applied to understand complex regional contexts. Practically, the conclusions of this research could inform political decision-makers, non-governmental organizations and international actors on the most appropriate strategies to promote stability and peace in the Great Lakes region. For example, a better understanding of local dynamics could guide more targeted and effective interventions (Birali, 2023).

In short, this three-level analysis offers a comprehensive perspective on factors contributing to insecurity in the Great Lakes region while providing recommendations for interventions adapted to each level of analysis.

2. Methods and Materials

This research used a qualitative research methodology, specifically a literature review. This approach was chosen to systematically analyze the existing scientific literature on the security dynamics of the Great Lakes region in Africa, focusing on the applicability of realist theory on three levels: individual, state and international. This study's primary data source comprised scientific articles, books, and reports published in peer-reviewed journals and reputable university presses. The collected data were analyzed using a thematic analysis approach.

3. Results

There are different forms of realistic theories. Beyond the simple difference between realistic authors, it is possible to identify several significant currents of realism. In particular, classical realism is organized around the thoughts of authors such as Hans Morgenthau, Edward Hallett Carr and Raymond Aron, and neorealism [or structural realism] with Kenneth Waltz as a reference figure. Classical and structural realism are two significant currents of realism in international relations, but their foundations and approaches to international policy differ.

3.1. Classical Realism and the Great Lakes Region of Africa

Classical realism emphasizes human nature as a source of conflict and power struggle. States act selfishly and seek to maximize their power because leaders are influenced by fundamental human motivations (interest, fear,

ambition). Therefore, international policy is a perpetual power struggle, but the states' decisions are shaped by their leaders and perceptions. Morgenthau insists on the importance of the morals and judgment of leaders in international politics (Morgenthau, 2014). Classical realism explains security instability in the Great Lakes region through competition for natural resources, mistrust between states, and the pursuit of power. For example, the presence of precious minerals such as coltan, gold, and diamonds has exacerbated tensions between countries such as the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), Rwanda, and Uganda. These states, seeking to maximize their power and ensure their security, often resort to offensive strategies, including support for armed groups and direct military intervention. This dynamic is consistent with the realist logic where states act selfishly to protect their national interests in an anarchic environment.

3.2. Neorealism [Structural Realism] and the Great Lakes Region of Africa

Unlike regions where a dominant power ensures stability [e.g., the U.S. in the Western Hemisphere], no single state in the Great Lakes region has consolidated enough power to impose order (C. Clapham, 1996). This encourages continued power struggles between countries like Rwanda, Uganda, and the Democratic Republic of Congo [DRC].

In addition, States in the region engage in proxy wars and support rebel groups as a strategic tool to counterbalance regional rivals (Lemarchand, 2009). For example, Rwanda and Uganda's interventions in the DRC can be interpreted as neorealist attempts to secure influence and preempt perceived threats.

Another neorealist point is Significant Power Influence. The neorealist balance of power concept is evident in how major external powers—such as China, the U.S., and the EU—engage with African states to secure economic and strategic interests rather than to promote peace (C. Clapham, 1996). For example, the scramble for coltan and other minerals perpetuates regional conflicts as external actors back different factions (A. J. R. o. A. P. E. Laudati, 2013).

3.2.1. Defensive Realism and the Great Lakes Region of Africa

Defensive realism, championed by Kenneth Waltz [1979], argues that states seek security rather than expansion, and conflict is often the result of misperceptions and overreactions to perceived threats rather than deliberate aggression (K. N. J. I. p. e. c. Waltz & issues, 1979).

While some analysts argue that Rwanda and Uganda have expansionist ambitions in the DRC, defensive realism suggests that a perception of insecurity drives their actions. Rwanda, for example, justifies its incursions into eastern Congo as preemptive measures against Hutu rebel groups linked to the 1994 genocide (Reyntjens, 2009). In addition, the Rwanda-Uganda intervention in the DRC [1998-2003] illustrates this, where both states justified military actions in the name of national security. However, their interventions exacerbated instability and prolonged the conflict (Reyntjens, 2009). Similarly, Burundi's post-2015 political crisis saw heightened border tensions as neighbouring countries feared spillover instability.

Defensive realism suggests that weak regional institutions [such as the African Union and ICGLR] fail to mediate conflicts effectively, leading states to engage in self-help strategies (C. Clapham, 1996).

Mistrust plays a significant part in prolonging conflicts. States' repeated interventions in the Great Lakes region can be understood as a result of deep-rooted mistrust, where states prefer preemptive actions over cooperative security arrangements (Lemarchand, 2009).

3.2.2. Offensive Realism and the Great Lakes Region of Africa

Offensive realism, developed by John Mearsheimer, takes a more aggressive stance. It argues that states are inherently power-maximizing and seek regional hegemony whenever possible (Mearsheimer, 2003). Unlike defensive realism, offensive realism interprets Rwanda's and Uganda's repeated military interventions in the DRC as active power-seeking strategies rather than mere defensive responses. The two states have actively sought to expand their influence in Eastern Congo, control economic resources, and project military dominance (Reyntjens, 2009). Similarly, the Central African Republic [CAR] has become a battleground for international actors, with Russia's Wagner Group and France vying for influence, further complicating national stability (Bouka, 2021). According to state fragility theory (Rotberg, 2004), failed states cannot exercise sovereignty, enforce laws, or provide essential services, leading to an environment where non-state actors thrive. The DRC, which possesses vast mineral wealth, has been unable to prevent armed groups from profiting from illicit mining (A. J. R. o. A. P. E. Laudati, 2013). The Central African Republic, ranked among the world's weakest states, has seen resource smuggling by rebel factions, further undermining governance (Bank, 2023). Empirical data from ACLED and SIPRI reports confirm that conflict intensity correlates with regions abundant in gold, coltan, and diamonds.

The persistent conflicts between states like the DRC, Rwanda, and Uganda suggest a struggle for regional dominance rather than purely defensive security posturing. This is evident in the Second Congo War [1998-2003], where multiple African states intervened in the DRC to assert influence (G. Prunier, 2008). Mearsheimer's argument that states pursue power whenever opportunities arise is relevant in the Great Lakes region (Mearsheimer, 2003), where control over resources like coltan and diamonds has incentivized states to engage in proxy warfare and direct military interventions (A. J. R. o. A. P. E. Laudati, 2013).

The Great Lakes region of Africa has been a persistent hotspot of conflict, characterized by cycles of violence, human rights abuses, and state failure. To understand the complex dynamics of this region, scholars have employed various theoretical frameworks, including realism. Realist theory, which emphasizes the role of power, self-interest, and state-centric competition, offers a valuable lens through which to analyze the region's security challenges.

However, while realist theory offers a valuable framework for understanding the region's security challenges, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations. A purely state-centric approach may overlook the role of non-state actors, such as armed groups and transnational criminal networks, which have significantly shaped the region's security landscape. Additionally, the influence of identity, culture, and history, often emphasized by constructivist and post-structuralist theories, cannot be entirely dismissed.

Recent scholarship has increasingly recognized the interplay between domestic and international factors in shaping the region's security dynamics. For instance, studies have highlighted the role of corruption, resource mismanagement, and weak governance in fueling conflict and instability (Collier & Hoeffler, 2004). Moreover, the impact of climate change and environmental degradation on the region's security has gained attention, as these factors can exacerbate existing tensions and lead to new conflicts (Work, 2019). Natural resource wealth, such as oil, diamonds, and minerals, can have a complex and often contradictory impact on African political stability. While these resources can generate significant revenue, they can also fuel corruption, inequality, and conflict. The relationship between natural resource wealth and political stability is contingent on various factors, including institutional quality, governance, and the specific characteristics of the resource. For instance, countries with strong institutions and effective governance may harness the benefits of natural resource wealth without compromising political stability. However, in countries with weak institutions and high levels of corruption, natural resources can exacerbate existing problems and lead to conflict (Epo & Nochi Faha, 2020). This is particularly evident in the Great Lakes region of Africa, where the exploitation of minerals, such as coltan and gold, has fueled violence and instability.

According to Wamalwa, the territorial disputes between Kenya and Uganda in Lake Victoria are based on resources, national sovereignty, issues of territorial integrity, and political agency. These elements have made it difficult to resolve the dispute amicably and have impacted the economic-political relations of the states. He recommends the intervention of a neutral arbitrator and adequate involvement of the third way in conflict resolution. He also suggests conducting further research on the ecological factors that influence the territorial disputes between Kenya and Uganda in Lake Victoria (Wamalwa, 2023). Transboundary conflicts extend to maritime areas shared by neighbouring countries. Most of these conflicts arise from the failure to manage the economic value of resources in shared naval regions. The transboundary conflicts in Lake Victoria between Kenya and Uganda concern resources in this maritime area. Equally important, the international community and national actors must recognise that water-related conflicts also erupt in water-rich regions. If efforts to limit these causes of conflict are not implemented in the short term, the risks that these conflicts will contribute to greater regional instability also increase (Renner, 2021). Kipchumba argues that water, land, and pasture are essential to their livelihoods and very often lead to frequent conflicts in the Kerio Valley, resulting in decreased production, increased casualties, deaths, displacement, and destruction of property, with youth, elders, and politicians very often being the leading actors (Kipchumba, 2019). According to Afolabi and Donkor, key stakeholders are sidelined from natural resource development, leading them to resort to violence. A viable approach is to combine indigenous knowledge and customs with feasible exogenous frameworks to facilitate effective management of natural resource conflicts. Natural resource conflicts can also be mitigated by promoting and adhering to principles of good governance, including participation, non-discrimination, transparency, accountability, legitimacy and legality. In most cases, natural resource conflicts start at the local level and must be resolved by involving relevant stakeholders in the conflict management process. In this regard, traditional community processes are considered ideal in local contexts and are, therefore, more easily adopted by communities (Afolabi & Donkor, 2021). According to Ombara, knowledge of sustainable management of shared resources is needed to avoid conflicts due to increasing resource demands, structural inequalities, and competition. The resulting peace lays the groundwork to unlock more opportunities and synergies, leading to more significant regional progress. Low compliance and enforcement of relevant regulations, differing resource management practices across borders, inadequate funding of programs, over-reliance on resources, and non-holistic approaches are the major contributors to the shrinking resource base in the context of population growth, competition for resources, and conflicts. Thus, well-managed resources promise stable livelihoods and economic well-being and help avoid competition and disagreements (Ombara, 2022).

3.3. Different realism theories and their applications to the Great Lakes region

Theory	Core Assumption	Application to the Great Lakes Region
Neorealism	The international system is anarchic; states seek security within a structured power balance.	Security competition among states, lack of a regional hegemon, and significant external power interference
Defensive Realism	States prioritize survival and act defensively to prevent threats.	Rwanda and Uganda's interventions in the DRC are defensive responses to perceived threats.
Offensive Realism	States maximize power and seek regional dominance whenever possible.	Rwanda and Uganda seek regional hegemony through military

		engagements and economic control.
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Source: By authors

Figure 1: Relationships between Realism, Neorealism, Defensive Realism, and Offensive Realism

Source: By authors

Figure 2: Country Behaviors and Realism Theories

Source: Empirical data on conflict trends, military expenditures, displaced populations, and the correlation between natural resources and conflict intensity in the Great Lakes region.

Figure 3: Conflict Trends in the Great Lakes Region

Source: By the authors

The data from the Armed Conflict Location & Event Data Project [ACLED] and Uppsala Conflict Data Program [UCDP] show a steady increase in conflict events from 2018 to 2024, with a particularly sharp rise from 2020 onwards. The increase in 2021–2024 coincides with political instability in the Democratic Republic of Congo [DRC], Rwanda, and Uganda, as well as the resurgence of armed groups such as the M23 rebels and ADF [Allied Democratic Forces]. The data suggest that regional rivalries and governance failures continue to fuel violence.

This aligns with neorealism, which states that the lack of a dominant power or regional hegemon leads to recurring security dilemmas.

Figure 4: military expenditures in the Great Lakes Region

Source: From by authors

The Stockholm International Peace Research Institute [SIPRI] has shown that military spending has steadily increased from \$3.1 billion in 2018 to \$6.2 billion in 2024. The rise in military expenditures coincides with increasing conflict intensity, particularly in DRC and border tensions among Rwanda, Uganda, and Burundi. Defensive realism suggests that states prioritize security through military buildup when external threats exist. Rwanda and Uganda have justified their military spending as necessary due to armed insurgencies in eastern DRC. The spike in 2022–2024 may be linked to great power competition, as external factors such as China, the US, and the EU fund military aid programs in the region [SIPRI, 2024; World Bank, 2023; Adebayo, 2023].

Figure 5: Displaced populations in the Great Lakes Region

Source: By authors

UNHCR [2024] stated that displaced persons increased from 4.5 million in 2018 to 7 million in 2024. The most significant spikes occurred between 2020 and 2024, aligning with intensifying conflicts in the DRC [M23, Mai-Mai, ADF], Burundi [political violence], and South Sudan's spillover effects. The rise in displacement is directly linked to conflict intensity, which confirms studies showing a high correlation between forced migration and insecurity. This trend suggests poor state capacity in the Great Lakes region as governments struggle to provide security and governance, reinforcing the state failure hypothesis.

Figure 6: Correlation between natural resources and conflict intensity in the Great Lakes region

Source: By authors

According to World Bank Data on Economic Indicators, the correlation between natural resource wealth and conflict intensity has increased from 0.62 in 2018 to 0.82 in 2024. This suggests that resource wealth [coltan, gold, and diamonds] increasingly drives conflict, supporting theories like the resource curse and greed vs. grievance.

Armed groups in eastern DRC continue to exploit minerals to finance war efforts, leading to increased international sanctions and UN investigations. Offensive realism explains this as states and non-state actors actively seeking power and economic control, as seen in Rwanda and Uganda's involvement in the DRC mining sectors.

4. Discussion

4.1. Realism at the Individual Level in the Great Lakes of Africa

At the individual level, realist theory suggests that leaders are primarily motivated by self-interest and power maximization. Realist theory suggests that leaders are mainly motivated by self-interest and power maximization (Morgenthau, 1973). In the Great Lakes region, this is evident in the actions of strongmen and authoritarian leaders who have often exploited ethnic and regional divisions to consolidate their power. For example, Mobutu Sese Seko's rule in Zaire [now the Democratic Republic of Congo] was characterized by corruption, nepotism, and the suppression of dissent, which contributed to the country's descent into conflict (Michel, 2000).

In the Great Lakes context, this is evident in the actions of strongmen and authoritarian rulers who have often exploited ethnic and regional divisions to consolidate their power (Barbé Martine, 1999). For instance, Mobutu

Sese Seko's rule in Zaire [now the Democratic Republic of Congo] was marked by corruption, nepotism, and the suppression of dissent, which contributed to the country's descent into conflict. From his early days in the volatile crucible of Zairian politics, Mobutu has shown a Machiavellian aptitude for creating and managing shifting coalitions of support, both within and outside. Other governments, international organizations, multinational businesses, and external entities such as the Catholic Church have complicated, fluctuating, and frequently competing economic, politico-strategic, and normative interests to protect the Zairian battlefield. The interstices generated by these different interest groups typically allow leeway for movement and autonomy for the absolutist king and his political aristocracy. Thus, Mobutu and his ruling elite have kept a significant degree of relative but shifting autonomy(Callaghy, 2013).

However, realist theory suggests that leaders are primarily motivated by self-interest and power maximization(KENNETH, 1967). In the Great Lakes region, this is evident in the actions of strongmen and authoritarian leaders who have often exploited ethnic and regional divisions to consolidate their power(Reyntjens, 2009). For example, Mobutu Sese Seko's rule in Zaire [now the Democratic Republic of Congo] was characterized by corruption, nepotism, and the suppression of dissent, which contributed to the country's descent into conflict(Naniuzeyi, 1999). Similarly, Laurent-Désiré Kabila's regime in the DRC was marked by violence and human rights abuses, further exacerbating regional tensions(G. r. Prunier, 1997).

Idi Amin attacked the Asians, mainly Indians and Pakistanis, who controlled most of the country's trade and were deported. Following their deportation, the country's economy collapsed because the Ugandans were not prepared and qualified to take over.

The Amin regime began to be criticized on the international level, especially by Great Britain, which is a former colonial power. Opponents within the country began to disappear, and Amin went so far as to attack Tanzania, accusing it of helping the rebels who wanted to bring back the former president Obote(Peterson, Gavua, & Rassool, 2015). Those were the main causes of the dictator's fall. The ambitions of some political leaders can damage the entire country.

In May 1990, as students staged a protest against Mobutu for rescinding his promise of bringing about democratic reforms, Mobutu's troops responded violently; nearly 300 students were killed. In the aftermath, both the US and France announced that further aid to Zaire would depend on Mobutu bringing about democratic reforms. Mobutu refused to cooperate, and his old allies in the West abandoned him, suspending foreign aid(Bustin, 2002). Many African countries suffer from poverty, not due to a lack of natural resources. An effective administration by the state through an able leader could go a long way in resolving the country's difficult situation. To sum up the conflict in the DRC between Mobutu and Kabila, not one of them put the country's interests above their own. Even if one of the three had done it, the country and the region would have seen not only peace but also economic development(Venugopalan, 2016). The effects of Mobutu's creation of a nationalistic stance in the 1960s and 1970s made for a strong image of unity within the initial decades of Zaire's independence. Despite this, these decades also represented signs of gross abuse of power that would affect not only the health and stability of the state but also the relationship the state had with its people(Trautman, 2013).

These leaders' pursuit of personal gain and political survival has often led to policies prioritising short-term interests over long-term stability, fueling cycles of conflict and instability. Furthermore, the presence of predatory

elites, such as warlords and militia leaders, who profit from the exploitation of natural resources and illicit trade, further complicates the security landscape(Collier & Hoeffler, 2004).

4.2. Realism at the National Level in the Great Lakes of Africa

At the national level, realist theory highlights the importance of state power and the pursuit of national interests. Realist theory emphasizes the importance of state power and the pursuit of national interests. In the Great Lakes region, states have often engaged in zero-sum competition, leading to a security dilemma where actions taken by one state to enhance its security are perceived as threats by others(K. N. Waltz, 1979). This dynamic has fueled regional arms races, proxy wars, and the proliferation of armed groups. As some scholars believe, a large concentration of power works for peace(W. C. J. J. o. C. W. S. Wohlforth, 1999), some countries in the region, for instance, Rwanda, seem to put more energy into empowering their military force as a way to maximize power in this region, which will further enhance its power unipolarity in the GLR. According to the neorealist-balance-of-power theory, unipolarity is a structure in which one state's capabilities are too excellent to be counterbalanced. At this point, Rwanda believes that any other country in the region cannot counterbalance it. Thus, they are forced to make peace irrespective of what Rwanda is accused of regarding regional security matters. Unfortunately, this may take a negative turn since excessive power poses a threat not only to its neighbouring countries but also to the region as a whole. In this line of thought, scholars believe that unipolarity is prone to conflict as other states seek to create a counterpoise to the overweening power of the leading state(W. C. Wohlforth, 2014).

In the Great Lakes region, states have often engaged in zero-sum competition, leading to a security dilemma where actions taken by one state to enhance its security are perceived as threats by others(Lemarchand, 2009). This dynamic has fueled regional arms races, proxy wars, and the proliferation of armed groups. Moreover, weak and failed states, such as the DRC and the Central African Republic, have provided fertile ground for the emergence of non-state actors and transnational criminal networks(Rotberg, 2004). However, realist theory emphasizes the importance of state power and the pursuit of national interests. In the Great Lakes region, states have often engaged in zero-sum competition, leading to a security dilemma where actions taken by one state to enhance its security are perceived as threats by others. This dynamic has fueled regional arms races, proxy wars, and the proliferation of armed groups(Lemarchand, 2009).

Moreover, weak and failed states, such as the DRC and the Central African Republic, have provided fertile ground for the emergence of non-state actors and transnational criminal networks. These states' inability to effectively exercise sovereignty and provide essential services has created a power vacuum, allowing armed groups to exploit resources, recruit fighters, and destabilize the region(Rotberg, 2004).

4.3. Realism at the International Level in the Great Lakes of Africa

At the international level, realist theory emphasizes the role of great powers in shaping global politics. Realist theory highlights the role of great powers in shaping global politics. Generally, the great powers' competition for influence on African countries is an undeniable geopolitical reality(Gavin, 2021). The rivalry and cooperation among them are the sparking cause of endless conflicts that have long characterized most African countries throughout history, so why not the current time? For instance, the presence of China and Russia on African soil bothers Western powers, and most of the time, they go even further by using coercive diplomacy, like cutting their cooperation aid once they continue to ally with what they paint as a 'Neocolonialism System'. This spirit of division often nourishes complex and endless conflicts among African countries. However, whether China, the

US or any other international partner, it is undeniably known that power is their ultimate aim. Moreover, while the Great Lakes region may not be a direct geopolitical battleground, the interests of external actors, such as China, the European Union, and the United States, have significant implications for regional security. These powers often pursue their strategic objectives by sometimes encouraging rivalry and cooperation, leading to a spirit of division among the regional state members. For instance, the international political actors' struggle for power may push them to undertake non-political means, like technical cooperation with other nations, to maximize their power in a given area. All these mechanisms are undertaken under the umbrella of 'protecting developing countries from the scourge of neocolonial wave'. Nonetheless, this is an open way to counterbalance their opponents with whom they share the same interests. And all of these bullshits are sometimes done at the expense of regional stability. As in realists' view, interest is the perennial standard by which political action must be judged and directed (Morgenthau, 1973). For example, the competition for natural resources, particularly minerals like coltan and gold, has fueled conflict and instability in the region (Lebert, 2027).

While the Great Lakes region may not be a direct geopolitical battleground, the interests of external actors, such as China, the European Union, and the United States, have significant implications for regional security. These powers often pursue their strategic objectives, sometimes at the expense of regional stability. For example, the competition for natural resources, particularly minerals like coltan and gold, has fueled conflict and instability in the region (A. Laudati, 2013)

However, realist theory highlights the role of great powers in shaping global politics (K. N. Waltz, 1979). While the Great Lakes region may not be a direct geopolitical battleground, the interests of external actors, such as China, the European Union, and the United States, have significant implications for regional security. These powers often pursue their strategic objectives, sometimes at the expense of regional stability (C. S. Clapham, 1996). For example, the competition for natural resources, particularly minerals like coltan and gold, has fueled conflict and instability in the region (C. S. Clapham, 1996). The inter-imperialist rivalry has played an essential role in the conflict of the DRC. Mwesiga Baregu states that there is a three-cornered imperialist rivalry in the Great Lakes region (Baregu). The four countries that comprise the Great Lakes region are the DRC, Burundi, Rwanda and Uganda ("Q&A: DR Congo conflict," 2012). On one side is the US, which has the ambition to be the most powerful country in the world and an insatiable appetite for strategic minerals. On the other side are the Franco-Belgium interests who want to maintain their foothold. In the third corner lies the United Kingdom [UK], which seeks to change the domination of France with assistance from the US (Fielding, 2015).

The AU Peace and Security Council [PSC] was established in 2004 to address security issues across Africa. It focuses on conflict prevention, peacekeeping, and post-conflict reconstruction.

The AU has been central in addressing conflicts in Sudan, Somalia, and the Great Lakes region. However, its interventions often lack enforceable power, and some critics argue that the AU's effectiveness is limited by inconsistent political will among member states.

For instance, the AU has attempted to broker peace in Darfur since 2005, but has been critically underfunded and lacks sufficient logistical and military capacity to implement peace agreements effectively (Mugabe, 2006). The other example is the AU Mission in Somalia [AMISOM], which has been relatively more successful. Still, challenges persist with regional rivalries and resource limitations.

Established in 2000, the ICGLR is a regional organization comprising 12 countries that addresses political, security, and socio-economic issues in the Great Lakes region. The ICGLR has been central to regional peacebuilding efforts, particularly in the DRC, Burundi, and Rwanda. However, its peacekeeping missions have often been ineffective due to a lack of resources and member-state commitment.

The ICGLR's attempts to broker peace during the Second Congo War were unsuccessful due to the complexity of local conflicts and the lack of unified action from regional leaders (Simmonds, 2015). In addition, despite the ICGLR's mandate to foster regional stability, political violence in Burundi in 2015 escalated primarily due to domestic political struggles that the ICGLR could not resolve.

The EAC is a regional intergovernmental organization established to promote economic integration, peace, and security among its member states: the DRC, Uganda, Tanzania, Rwanda, and Burundi. It has effectively promoted economic cooperation, but political divisions and lacking military capacity have limited its security interventions. According to Vlavon [2016], the EAC's response to the political crisis in Burundi was inconclusive, as Tanzania and Uganda's differing political interests led to conflicting views on intervention strategies (Vlavon, 2016). The United Nations Organization Stabilization Mission in the Democratic Republic of the Congo [MONUSCO], the largest UN peacekeeping operation in the world, was established in 2010 to support peacekeeping, humanitarian aid, and stability efforts in the DRC (Gowan, 2017). It has faced significant challenges, including limited mandates, insufficient resources, and local distrust. Despite large troop deployments, the mission has not entirely curbed violence in eastern DRC. MONUSCO's limited ability to protect civilians in Kivu between 2018 and 2021 has raised concerns about the effectiveness of international peacekeeping in complex, non-state-driven conflicts.

The UN Peacekeeping mission has been in Congo since 1999. It has deployed around 20,000 personnel in the country and is one of the most significant peacekeeping operations in the world. However, a 2009 report by UN experts has mentioned that the UN Special Forces have not done anything substantial to reduce or stop the violence since the rebels are continuing to kill and loot the country's natural resources. The Congolese government wants the UN forces to leave the DRC and claims it can maintain law and order (Misser, 2015).

Concerning Peacekeeping operations, realist predictions often suggest that missions fail when they are not backed by strong national interests or coercive power. MONUSCO struggles despite its large size and mandate because of a lack of political will and external interventions that do not align with the mission's goals (Gowan, 2017). Proxy wars and external interventions in the DRC and surrounding regions align with realist predictions that states and external actors act out of self-interest rather than altruistic peacekeeping motives.

Conclusion

Analyzing the Great Lakes region through a realist lens reveals a complex interplay of power politics, state-centric competition, and the pursuit of self-interest. As anticipated by realist theory, the region has been plagued by cycles of violence, state failure, and human rights abuses. The actions of individual leaders, such as Mobutu Sese Seko and Laurent-Désiré Kabila, have significantly contributed to these challenges. Their pursuit of personal power and the suppression of dissent have exacerbated tensions and undermined stability. At the national level, the security dilemma, characterized by a spiral of mistrust and arms races, has been a persistent feature of the region. States have often prioritized their security interests over regional cooperation, leading to conflicts and instability. Weak and failed states, such as the Democratic Republic of Congo and the Central African Republic, have provided fertile ground for the emergence of non-state actors, further complicating the security landscape.

International factors have also played a significant role in shaping the region's security dynamics. Great power competition, particularly over natural resources, has fueled conflict and instability. While international interventions have sometimes sought to address these challenges, their impact has been mixed. Peacekeeping operations have often struggled to prevent violence and promote sustainable peace. However, while realist theory provides a valuable framework for understanding the region's security challenges, it is essential to acknowledge its limitations. A purely state-centric approach may overlook the role of non-state actors, such as armed groups and transnational criminal networks, which have significantly shaped the region's security landscape. Additionally, the influence of identity, culture, and history, often emphasized by constructivist and post-structuralist theories, cannot be entirely dismissed. A multi-faceted approach is necessary to address the Great Lakes region's complex security challenges. This should include strengthening state institutions, promoting good governance, and addressing the root causes of conflict, such as poverty, inequality, and environmental degradation. International cooperation is also crucial, but it must be tailored to the region's specific needs and avoid imposing one-size-fits-all solutions. Future research should delve deeper into the interplay between domestic and international factors, exploring the impact of climate change, globalization, and emerging technologies on the region's security. By combining insights from various theoretical perspectives, scholars can develop more nuanced and comprehensive understandings of the complex dynamics at play in the Great Lakes region. Realist theory provides a valuable framework for understanding the complex security dynamics of the Great Lakes region of Africa. By focusing on the role of power, interests, and state behaviour at multiple levels of analysis, we can gain valuable insights into the enduring instability that plagues the region. However, it is essential to acknowledge the limitations of realism, particularly its tendency to overemphasize state-centric factors and neglect the role of non-state actors and transnational forces. A more nuanced understanding of the region's security challenges requires a multidisciplinary approach incorporating insights from other theoretical perspectives, such as constructivism and liberalism.

References

- Afolabi, O. A., & Donkor, F. K. (2021). Natural Resources as Instruments for Social Cohesion and Peace Building. *African Journal of Sustainable Development*, 11(3), 69-87.
- Bank, W. (2023). Africa's Political Economy and Security Assistance Report.
- Barbé Martine, L. S., Michel Thierry, Pireaux Christine. (1999). Mobutu, King of Zaire: African tragedy [Press release]. Retrieved from https://wrlc-gwu.primo.exlibrisgroup.com/discovery/fulldisplay?context=L&docid=alma9977294123604107&lang=en&search_scope=DN_and_CI&tab=Everything&vid=01WRLC_GWA:live
- Baregu, M. History of the Conflict *Eastern Congo Initiative*.
- Birali, P. H. (2023). Défis et Opportunités pour une paix durable dans la Région des Grands Lacs. Points de vue des populations du Kivu montagneux. *Pole Institute Institut Interculturel dans la Région des Grands Lacs*.

Jacques Magabo, Patrick Mushitsi, Vèrene Niyomana, Régis Bayihaye and Jean-Claude Ntizoyimana (2025)

- Bouka, Y. (2021). Women, colonial resistance, and decolonization: Challenging African histories. In *The Palgrave Handbook of African Women's Studies* (pp. 1295-1313): Springer.
- Bustin, E. J. R. o. A. P. E. (2002). Remembrance of sins past: unravelling the murder of Patrice Lumumba. *29(93-94)*, 537-560.
- Callaghy, T. M. (2013). External actors and the relative autonomy of the political aristocracy in Zaire. In *State and Class in Africa* (pp. 61-83): Routledge.
- Clapham, C. (1996). *Africa and the International System: The Politics of State Survival*: Cambridge University Press.
- Clapham, C. S. (1996). *Africa and the international system: The politics of state survival*: Cambridge University Press.
- Collier, P., & Hoeffler, A. (2004). Greed and grievance in civil war. *Oxford economic papers*, *56(4)*, 563-595.
- Epo, B. N., & Nochi Faha, D. R. (2020). Natural resources, institutional quality, and economic growth: An African tale. *The European Journal of Development Research*, *32(1)*, 99-128.
- Fielding, A. (2015). Could the DRC be Africa's Next third Term Battleground? . *IPI Global Observatory*.
- Gavin, M. D. (2021). Major Power Rivalry in Africa. *Discussion Paper Series on Managing Global Disorder*, No.5.
- Gowan, R. (2017). The UN and the DRC: A Realist Perspective. *International Peacekeeping Journal*, *24(2)*, 25–43.
- KENNETH, W. T. (1967). POLITICS AMONG NATIONS: THE STRUGGLE FOR POWER AND PEACE. In: JSTOR.
- Kipchumba, B. J. (2019). *An analysis of local dynamics in conflicts over use of natural resources in the marakwet-pokot border region of kerio valley, kenya*. University of Nairobi,
- Laudati, A. (2013). Beyond minerals: broadening ‘economies of violence in eastern Democratic Republic of Congo. *Review of African Political Economy*, *40(135)*, 32-50.
- Laudati, A. J. R. o. A. P. E. (2013). Beyond minerals: broadening ‘economies of violence in eastern Democratic Republic of Congo. *40(135)*, 32-50.
- Lebert, J. (2027). *Conflict-Prone Minerals in the Great*

Jacques Magabo, Patrick Mushitsi, Vèrène Niyomana, Régis Bayihaye and Jean-Claude Ntizoyimana (2025)

- Lakes Region of Africa*. Retrieved from <https://impacttransform.org/wp-content/uploads/2017/09/Briefing-Note-Conflict-Prone-Minerals-in-the-Great-Lakes-Region-of-Africa.pdf>
- Lemarchand, R. (2009). *The dynamics of violence in Central Africa*: University of Pennsylvania Press.
- Levine, D. H., & Nagar, D. (2015). *SÉCURITÉ ET GOUVERNANCE DANS LA RÉGION DES GRANDS LACS*. Retrieved from <http://www.jstor.org/stable/resrep05132>
- Mearsheimer, J. J. (2003). *The tragedy of great power politics (Updated edition)*: WW Norton & Company.
- Michel, T. (2000). Mobutu, King of Zaire - Part 1 [Press release]. Retrieved from <https://icarusfilms.com/if-mob1>
- Misser, F. (2015). Congo-Kinshasa: Articles of Faith. *Africa in Fact*.
- Morgenthau, H. J. (1973). *Politics among nations*.
- Morgenthau, H. J. (2014). A realist theory of international politics. In *The realism reader* (pp. 53-59): Routledge.
- Mugabe, D. (2006). African Union and the Darfur Peace Process. *African Journal of Political Science and International Relations*, 13(4), 21–34.
- Naniuzeyi, M. E. (1999). The state of the state in Congo-Zaire: A survey of the Mobutu regime. *Journal of black studies*, 29(5), 669-683.
- Ombara, I. (2022). How Management of Cross Border Natural Resources Affects Sustainable Peace: An Overview of Eastern Africa Region. *Journal for Peace and Justice Studies*, 31(2), 99-125.
- Peterson, D. R., Gavua, K., & Rassool, C. (2015). The Politics of Heritage in Africa: economies, histories, and infrastructures.
- Prunier, G. (2008). *Africa's world war: Congo, the Rwandan genocide, and the making of a continental catastrophe*: Oxford University Press.
- Prunier, G. r. (1997). The Rwanda Crisis: History of a Genocide. *Columbia UP*.
- Q&A: DR Congo conflict. (2012). *BBC NWES*.
- Renner, J. (2021). A conflict over water in water abundant regions: The case of Lake Naivasha in Kenya and Lake Wamala in Uganda.
- Reyntjens, F. (2009). *The great African war: Congo and regional geopolitics, 1996-2006*: Cambridge University Press.

- Rotberg, R. I. (2004). *State failure and state weakness in a time of terror*: Rowman & Littlefield.
- Simmonds, P. (2015). Regional Organizations and Peacekeeping in Africa: A Case Study of the ICGLR. *Journal of African Security Studies*, 8(2), 50–64.
- Trautman, A. Z. (2013). *From Zaire to the DRC: A case study of state failure*: University of South Florida.
- Venugopalan, H. (2016). Understanding the conflict in Congo.
- Wlavon, C. (2016). Security and Diplomacy in East Africa: The EAC's Role in the Burundi Crisis. *African Security Review*, 25(3), 60–72.
- Waltz, K. N. (1979). The anarchic structure of world politics. *International politics: enduring concepts and contemporary issues*, 29-49.
- Waltz, K. N. J. I. p. e. c., & issues, c. (1979). The anarchic structure of world politics. 29-49.
- Wamalwa, J. C. (2023). *Dynamics Of Lake Victoria Territorial Disputes On Kenya-Uganda Econo-Political Relations*. Kisii University,
- Wohlforth, W. C. (2014). The stability of a unipolar world. In *The Realism Reader* (pp. 383-395): Routledge.
- Wohlforth, W. C. J. J. o. C. W. S. (1999). A particular idea of science: How international relations theory avoids the New Cold War history. *I*(2), 39-60.
- Work, C. (2019). Climate change and conflict: Global insecurity and the road less traveled. *Geoforum*, 102, 222-225.